

Optical Fiber Induced Noise in RF-Photonic Links

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1. Introduction

Analog radio frequency (RF) over fiber link systems have shown promise in aviation applications for RF Radar signal distribution within aircraft. These RF-photonic links usually requires relatively high optical power (0.1 to 1W) for the laser carrier in order to increase the spur-free-dynamic-range (SFDR) and reduce the noise figure of the link system. However, these high power levels lead to nonlinear scattering in optical fiber that induces additional noise on the optical signal traveling through the fiber. This additional optical noise is converted into RF noise after photodetection. In this work, we present experimental data demonstrating optical-scattering-induced noise in high-power RF-photonic links.

We present data showing noise induced by both stimulated Rayleigh scattering (STRS) and stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS) [1, 2]. This scattering-induced noise is dependent on both the length of optical fiber used in the RF-photonic link and the optical power transmitted through the fiber. At power levels above 200 mW, fiber links as short as 40 m induced significant intensity noise on the optical signal.

In addition, we investigate techniques for the suppression of scattering induced noise in optical fiber. In particular, we show that frequency modulation of the laser signal suppresses both STRS and SBS by several orders of magnitude. Such scattering suppression techniques must be employed in high-power low-noise RF-photonic links in order to maintain the fidelity of RF signals transmitted over fiber.

2. Stimulated Rayleigh and Brillouin Scattering

Rayleigh scattering can be described as scattering of incident light off of stationary density fluctuations in the optical fiber [2]. Whenever light approaches the boundary between two regions with different indices of refraction, a portion of the light is reflected off of the interface. Since the dimensions of these density fluctuations are on the order of the wavelength of the incident light, the light can be scattered in many directions. Since these density fluctuations are located randomly along the length of the fiber, the induced scattering generates phase and amplitude noise. The density fluctuations can themselves be induced by the incident light via electrostriction leading to stimulated Rayleigh scattering (STRS). The limited data in the literature on Rayleigh scattering in optical fiber suggests that the Rayleigh gain bandwidth is on the order of 10 kHz [3]. In addition, because the density fluctuations are nearly stationary, Rayleigh scattering does not induce a significant frequency shift in the scattered light. The fiber-induced noise we measure within 10 kHz from the optical carrier is primarily due to Rayleigh scattering.

Brillouin scattering is caused by the interaction between the incident light and phonons within the fiber [2]. These phonons can be thought of as moving density fluctuations as opposed to the stationary density fluctuations that cause Rayleigh scattering. Because phonons have a finite energy, the interaction induces a frequency shift in the scattered light. This frequency shift is approximately 11 GHz in optical fiber. Due to the conservation of both energy and momentum, the finite phonon momentum causes Brillouin scattering to occur primarily in the counter-propagating direction. At approximately 10 MHz, the Brillouin scattering bandwidth is significantly greater than that of Rayleigh scattering. In addition to inducing noise at 11 GHz from the optical carrier, Brillouin scattering also generates noise within 10 MHz of the carrier by randomly depleting the incident light beam. As in the case of Rayleigh scattering, the incident light can amplify phonons via electrostriction thereby leading to stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS). The fiber-induced noise we measure beyond 10 kHz from the optical carrier is primarily due to Brillouin scattering.

3. Effects of Optical Scattering on Transmitted Noise Sepctra

In order to determine the effect of optical scattering on the noise spectra of RF-photonic links, we measured the intensity noise of a laser signal after propagation along fiber spools of varying lengths. Fig. 1 shows a schematic diagram of our measurement setup. Light from a 200 mW fiber laser is passed through the fiber under test. The output from the fiber is then split in two and sent to a pair of photodetectors. The output signals from the photodetectors are then sent to a pair of low noise AC-coupled amplifiers. These AC-coupled amplifiers filter out the DC current from the photodetectors leaving only the AC noise portion of the photodiode currents. The output signals from the two amplifiers are then sent to a phase-sensitive electrical spectrum analyzer. The spectrum analyzer then

performs a cross-correlation on the two signals. This cross-correlation suppresses any noise induced in the photodetectors and amplifiers leaving only the noise to the laser and the fiber under test.

Fig. 1. A schematic diagram of our transmitted intensity noise measurement setup.

We used standard Corning single mode fiber in all of our measurements. We varied the lengths of fiber while keeping the input optical power fixed at 200 mW. Fig. 2 shows plots of the measured intensity noise between 10 Hz and 1 MHz from the optical carrier for four different lengths of optical fiber. For a 1 m fiber link, the transmitted noise is essentially just the relative intensity noise of the fiber laser. However, when the fiber lengths is increased to 40 m, we observe increased intensity noise between 10 Hz and 1 kHz. This increased noise is induced by Rayleigh scattering. When the fiber length is increased to 500 m, the Rayleigh-induced noise increases further. In addition, we observe increased noise beyond the 10 kHz Rayleigh bandwidth which is caused by Brillouin scattering depleting the incident beam. Finally, for a 6 km link, we see increased noise over the entire frequency range from 10 Hz to 1 MHz. In addition, we observe Fresnel fringes caused by interference between double Brillouin scattered light and the incident light beam. This measured noise would be imprinted onto any RF signal via beating between the optical carrier and any modulation sidebands.

Fig. 2. Plots of transmitted power spectra through single-mode optical fiber of varying lengths. The transmitter used a 200 mW laser. Rayleigh-scattering induced noise is observed for fiber lengths as short as 40 m. For longer lengths of fiber, Brillouin-induced noise is also observed.

4. References

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